

MS6 - Sustainability Plan

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Consortium members

Acronym Partner

EMBL EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY

BIOBYTE BIOBYTE SOLUTIONS GMBH

HPCNOW HPC NOW CONSULTING SL

UO UNIVERSITETET I OSLO

UB UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA

ZBMED INFORMATION CENTRE FOR LIFE SCIENCE

Rlcapacity Rlcapacity

ALU-FR ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG

EPFL ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE

Table of Contents

About this report.....	2
Consortium members.....	2
Table of Contents.....	3
Project Overview.....	4
Preface.....	4
Sustainability, Long-Term Impact, and Continuation.....	4
Objectives.....	4
Training Materials.....	4
Reuse by Third Parties.....	5
Community Continuation.....	5
Emerging Initiatives and Spin-offs.....	5
Key Findings.....	5

Project Overview

The BioNT consortium is dedicated to providing a comprehensive training program and fostering a community for digital skills relevant to the biotechnology industry and biomedical sector. With a curriculum tailored for both beginners and advanced professionals, BioNT aims to equip individuals with the necessary expertise in handling, processing, and visualising biological data, as well as utilising computational biology tools. Leveraging the consortium's strong background in digital literacy training and extensive network of collaborations, BioNT is poised to professionalise life sciences data management, processing, and analysis skills.

Preface

This report documents the sustainability plan and final project communication published at the close of the BioNT project, fulfilling Milestone 6 (MS6) of Work Package 7. It describes the arrangements made to ensure that BioNT's outputs, community relationships, and training infrastructure remain accessible and functional beyond the EU funding period, which concludes in June 2026. The intended readership encompasses consortium partners, the European Commission, and the wider public, including training communities and professionals with an interest in digital skills development for the biotechnology and biomedical sectors.

Sustainability, Long-Term Impact, and Continuation

Objectives

Sustainability was a design principle of BioNT from the outset and has informed infrastructure, licensing, and community decisions throughout the project period. The arrangements described in this report ensure that the project's outputs remain accessible and functional beyond the funding period. No follow-on funded project is planned.

Training Materials

All BioNT training materials are openly licensed under Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) and will remain accessible through two principal hosting arrangements, determined by the framework in which they were developed. Materials developed using the Galaxy Training Network framework will be hosted, archived, and maintained as part of GTN's ongoing infrastructure, ensuring they remain synchronised with the evolving GTN ecosystem and discoverable by its large international user community. Materials developed using The Carpentries framework will be permanently hosted on the BioNT Training GitHub organisation space, providing version-controlled, openly accessible hosting independent of BioNT's project infrastructure. All lessons are linked from the BioNT Training Portal (biont-training.eu/training.html), maintained by ZB MED, who commits to hosting the website for a minimum of five years beyond the project end date. Video recordings for all 12 courses

are hosted on the Lhumos platform (lhumos.org/spaces/biont), maintained by EPFL, whose ongoing hosting commitment ensures these resources remain available to independent learners beyond the project period. The basic curriculum materials are available in English, German, Spanish, and Italian. Translated materials are hosted alongside the English originals and are maintained through the same long-term hosting arrangements.

Reuse by Third Parties

The consortium's experiences and lessons learnt in designing online and self-paced learning formats have been documented separately (Müller & Müller, 2026; <https://zenodo.org/records/19334986>), intended to enable other training communities to benefit from these insights beyond the BioNT context. The BioNT Training Portal also provides a self-assessment checklist for course alignment with the European Council's micro-credentials requirements, supporting future training providers in designing courses to that standard.

Community Continuation

The relationships built through the project, with The Carpentries, the Galaxy Training Network, CodeRefinery, ELIXIR, de.NBI, and industry partners, represent the community infrastructure that BioNT has developed alongside its materials. These connections extend the project's reach well beyond the nine consortium partners and provide the basis for continued uptake and adaptation of BioNT's training resources by others. The trained instructors and helpers who participated across 12 course deliveries constitute a further legacy: a distributed pool of practitioners with direct experience of the BioNT training model, capable of replicating or adapting it independently. BioNT's model (open materials, community-embedded infrastructure, iterative quality improvement, and multi-language accessibility) is directly transferable to other training initiatives within the Digital Europe Programme and the broader ELIXIR and life sciences training ecosystems.

Emerging Initiatives and Spin-offs

VINTSYS, an Oslo-based AI start-up, was registered in the Norwegian business registry ("Brønnøysundregistrene") as a spin-off that utilises BioNT learning materials. The founder has begun leveraging materials from the BioNT Applied Machine Learning course to develop an intelligent, self-paced learning assistant based on Retrieval-Augmented Generation. This represents an early example of third-party reuse of BioNT outputs for purposes beyond the original project scope, and demonstrates the potential for BioNT materials to underpin novel learning applications developed by others.

Key Findings

The measures implemented under MS6 confirm that BioNT has established durable arrangements for the continuation of its outputs and community beyond the project period. Key outcomes include:

- All training materials are openly licensed (CC-BY) and hosted through long-term arrangements with GTN, the BioNT GitHub organisation, ZB MED, and EPFL
- The BioNT Training Portal will remain accessible for a minimum of five years beyond project end, maintained by ZB MED
- Video recordings for all 12 courses are available on the Lhumos platform for independent learners
- Multilingual materials (English, German, Spanish, Italian) are maintained through the same hosting arrangements as the English originals
- Community relationships with The Carpentries, GTN, CodeRefinery, ELIXIR, and de.NBI provide the basis for continued uptake and adaptation of BioNT resources
- A trained and distributed pool of instructors and helpers ensures the BioNT training model can be replicated independently
- Third-party reuse is already evidenced by the VINTSYS spin-off, which is building on BioNT Applied Machine Learning materials
- Documented lessons learnt (Müller & Müller, 2026) are publicly available to support other training communities